

Inhibitive Action of Benzimidazole and its Derivatives on the Corrosion and Dezincification of 70/30 Brass in Ammonia

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Manuscript received 11 May 1992, revised 18 August 1992, accepted 17 September 1992

The inhibitive action of benzimidazole (BIA), and some of its derivatives, viz. 2-aminobenzimidazole (ABIA), 2-hydroxybenzimidazole (HBIA) and 5-carboxybenzimidazole (CBIA) towards corrosion and dezincification of 70/30 brass in ammonia solution has been investigated using weight-loss, solution analysis and galvanostatic polarisation techniques. All the compounds have been found to follow langmuir adsorption isotherm and behave as mixed inhibitors. Inhibitive efficiency was found to follow the order ; ABIA > HBIA > BIA > CBIA.

Brasses containing more than 15% zinc when exposed to corrosive environments, undergo not only general corrosion damage, but also suffer from dezincification¹—a process involving preferential dissolution of zinc leaving behind a spongy mass of copper on the surface of the alloy. This de-alloying of brass is associated with stress corrosion cracking² causing machine failure. Brasses are known to undergo this type of failure readily in ammoniacal environment. The problem has been addressed both from metallurgical³ and electrochemical considerations. It is generally known that organic compounds containing one or more polar atoms, e.g. N, S or O and compounds containing π -bond can afford protection against corrosion of metals. The studies on inhibition of corrosion and dezincification of brass in ammonia have been reported⁴. In spite of numerous attempts made so far, the problem is considered to be largely unresolved. The present paper deals with a comparative study of the inhibitive effect of benzimidazole (BIA), 2-aminobenzimidazole (ABIA), 2-hydroxybenzimidazole (HBIA) and 5-carboxybenzimidazole (CBIA) on the corrosion and dezincification of brass in ammonia solution.

Results and Discussion

Most of the studies reported in the literature on corrosion and dezincification of brass in ammonia were restricted to 13.4 *N* ammonia. No doubt dissolution of brass increases with increasing concentration of ammonia, but it is interesting to note that concentration of ammonia appears to play a dual role in stimulating corrosion and as also inhibition, albeit in presence of the organic additives. This is apparent from Fig. 1 where the corrosion rate of brass in mdd ($\text{mg dm}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$) and also the inhibitive efficiency of the inhibitors have been plotted as a function of ammonia concentration. The corrosion rate was found to increase from 72.6 to 106.9 mdd in passing from 1 *N* to 13.4 *N* ammonia. There exists a parallelism also in the

inhibitive process, e.g. the corresponding percent inhibition efficiency with 10^{-3} *M* ABIA was found to increase from 65.23 to 72.51%. This trend was quite general and valid for all the inhibitors studied. This implies that the inhibitors are more effective in concentrated ammonia solution. The benzimidazoles, employed in the present investigation, are very weak bases and, therefore, readily undergo deprotonation in ammonia, e.g. for BIA with $\text{p}K_a = 5.6$ at 25°, the reaction, $\text{BIA} \rightleftharpoons \text{BIA}^- + \text{H}^+$ is favoured by increasing concentration of ammonia liberating more of BIA^- ions which subsequently enter into stable complex formation with the components of the alloy conferring resistance to corrosion. Thus the inhibition efficiency is expected to improve with increasing concentration of ammonia at a given inhibitor concentration.

The effect of ammonia concentration upon dezincification with and without inhibitors has been shown in Fig. 2. It can be seen that dezincification proceeds more readily in dilute ammonia than in concentrated solution, and in presence of the inhibitors, the dezincification factor reaches a maximum at about 5 *N* ammonia solution. These observations lead to the conclusion that dissolution of zinc is favoured by dilute ammonia whereas that of copper is favoured by concentrated ammonia solution.

Representative Langmuir plots for the inhibitors in 1 *N* ammonia at 30° are shown in Fig. 3. The surface coverage (θ) at a bulk concentration (*C*) of the inhibitors was calculated directly from the inhibitive efficiency derived from weight-loss measurements. Both ABIA and HBIA exhibited a surface coverage of about 71% at an inhibitor concentration of as low as 10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} . The surface coverage exhibited by BIA and CBIA were, however, relatively small. The linearity of the $\log [\theta/(1-\theta)]$ vs $\log C$ plots suggests that inhibition is caused by the additives, being chemisorbed on the surface of the brass.

The results of solution analysis in respect of dezincification and effect of the inhibitors thereon

Fig. 1. Dependence of corrosion of brass and its inhibition upon concentration of ammonia. Rate of corrosion in (●) ammonia; P.I.: (Δ) BIA, (□) ABIA, (○) HBIA and (∇) CBIA.

Fig. 2. Dependence of dezincification factor upon concentration of ammonia: (●) without inhibitor; with inhibitor (10^{-3} M): (Δ) BIA, (□) ABIA, (○) HBIA and (∇) CBIA.

Fig. 3. Langmuir adsorption isotherm for corrosion inhibition of brass in 1 N ammonia : (Δ) BIA, (\square) ABIA, (\circ) HBIA and (∇) CBIA.

TABLE I - RESULTS OF IMMERSION TEST AND SOLUTION ANALYSIS IN 1 N AMMONIA SOLUTION WITH AND WITHOUT INHIBITOR

Temp. = 30°, immersion period = 24 h

Inhibitor concn. M	Wt. loss mg	P.I.	Solution analysis		\bar{Z}	P.I. Cu	P.I. Zn
			Cu $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Zn $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$			
Without inhibitor	5.81	—	24.20	14.6	1.41	—	—
BIA 10^{-6}	3.07	47.16	13.13	7.33	1.80	45.73	49.77
10^{-5}	2.95	49.23	13.27	6.40	1.12	45.17	56.16
10^{-4}	2.61	55.07	12.86	4.53	0.82	46.83	68.94
10^{-3}	2.26	61.10	12.00	3.07	0.59	50.41	79.00
10^{-2}	2.03	65.00	11.00	2.53	0.52	54.50	82.64
ABIA 10^{-6}	2.98	48.64	13.00	6.20	1.23	46.28	57.34
10^{-5}	2.41	58.52	10.86	5.20	1.12	55.09	64.38
10^{-4}	2.30	60.39	11.00	4.33	0.91	54.54	70.31
10^{-3}	2.02	65.23	10.67	2.80	0.62	55.92	80.82
10^{-2}	1.72	70.34	9.26	2.20	0.55	61.70	84.93
HBIA 10^{-6}	3.77	35.15	14.86	10.27	1.20	38.56	29.68
10^{-5}	3.20	44.92	14.67	6.67	1.06	39.40	54.34
10^{-4}	2.50	57.00	11.80	4.87	0.96	51.24	66.67
10^{-3}	2.15	62.92	11.20	3.13	0.65	53.72	73.58
10^{-2}	1.68	71.13	8.93	2.27	0.58	63.08	84.47
CBIA 10^{-6}	4.04	30.51	16.80	10.13	1.18	30.58	30.59
10^{-5}	3.78	34.93	17.33	7.93	1.07	23.40	45.66
10^{-4}	3.50	39.75	16.33	7.00	1.00	32.50	52.65
10^{-3}	3.08	46.89	15.54	4.99	0.75	35.75	65.82
10^{-2}	2.40	58.69	12.40	3.53	0.66	48.48	75.80

(Table 1) reveal that all the imidazoles employed in the present investigation are able to minimise the dissolution of both Cu and Zn, and the inhibitive effect increases with increasing concentration of the inhibitors. Furthermore, these are excellent agents for inhibiting dezincification of brass as is reflected in the values of the dezincification factors (Z), e.g. Z-values of 1.1–1.3 could be achieved at an inhibitor concentration of as low as 10^{-6} mol dm $^{-3}$ and the Z-values at an inhibitor concentration of 10^{-9} mol dm $^{-3}$ were in the range 0.53–0.56. The percent inhibition efficiency against dissolution of Zn was correspondingly high as compared to that against dissolution of Cu. The inhibition efficiencies of BIA, ABIA, HBIA and CBIA in 1 N ammonia at 30° as obtained from weight-loss measurements are also shown in Table 1. The inhibiting effectiveness seem to follow the order : ABIA > HBIA > BIA > CBIA. With the same inhibitor concentration, the efficiency is expected to be still greater at higher concentrations of ammonia as has already been demonstrated.

Typical polarisation curves for 70/30 brass in 1 N ammonia at 30° without and with inhibitors at a concentration of 10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$ have been shown in Figs. 4 and 5. All the inhibitors were found to inhibit both anodic and cathodic reactions indicating thereby a mixed type of inhibition. The results of polarisation have been recorded in Table 2. All the inhibitors were found to reduce the corrosion

Fig. 5. Galvanostatic polarisation curves for 70/30 brass in 1 N ammonia without and with 10^{-3} M inhibitors at 30° : (●) without inhibitors ; with inhibitor : (○) HBIA and (▽) CBIA.

Fig. 4. Galvanostatic polarisation curves for 70/30 brass in 1 N ammonia without and with 10^{-3} M inhibitors at 30° : (●) without inhibitor ; with inhibitor : (Δ) BIA and (□) ABIA.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF POLARISATION MEASUREMENTS IN 1 N AMMONIA SOLUTION WITH AND WITHOUT INHIBITORS
Temp. = 30°

Inhibitor concn. M	Open-circuit potential (S.C.E.) mV	Corrosion current $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$	P.I.
Without inhibitor	-506	38.51	—
BIA 10^{-6}	-510	20.41	47.00
10^{-5}	-511	19.17	50.22
10^{-4}	-516	15.60	59.48
10^{-3}	-521	12.57	67.35
ABIA 10^{-6}	-513	20.18	47.60
10^{-5}	-515	16.17	58.00
10^{-4}	-519	13.81	64.12
10^{-3}	-529	9.80	74.55
HBIA 10^{-6}	-513	25.34	34.20
10^{-5}	-517	21.18	45.00
10^{-4}	-518	16.68	58.70
10^{-3}	-525	11.81	69.85
CBIA 10^{-6}	-508	29.99	28.90
10^{-5}	-513	25.42	34.00
10^{-4}	-515	22.00	42.85
10^{-3}	-523	18.33	52.39

current which again decreases with increasing concentration of the inhibitors. The percent inhibition efficiency calculated from corrosion current was found to follow the same order of effectiveness as was obtained from weight-loss measurements. In

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF CORROSION CURRENT WITH AMMONIA CONCENTRATION FOR 70/30 BRASS WITHOUT AND WITH INHIBITORS ($10^{-5} M$)

Inhibitor	1 N		5 N		9 N		13.36 N	
	i_{corr} $\mu A cm^2$	P.I.						
Without inhibitor	38.51	—	48.23	—	51.23	—	64	—
BIA	12.57	67.35	14.67	68.25	15.45	69.89	16.04	71.90
ABIA	9.80	74.55	13.49	70.80	12.80	75.00	13.82	78.30
HBIA	11.61	69.85	14.33	69.00	14.28	72.12	16.61	73.20
CBIA	18.33	52.39	22.65	51.00	22.49	56.09	26.04	58.00

conformity with immersion tests, polarisation studies also revealed that corrosion current and percent inhibition are influenced by concentration of ammonia as has been shown in Table 3.

It is generally accepted that inhibition of corrosion is achieved by adsorption of the inhibitors on to the surface of the corroding metal (or alloy). It has been shown that the adsorption of inhibitor molecules reduces the number of electrode reaction sites⁷ and inhibition becomes the dominant process when the metal surface is covered with nearly a monolayer of the inhibitor.

In the presence of the inhibitors, some coloured films were invariably observed on the surface of the specimens. The nature of the colour was however different depending upon the inhibitor, e.g. with BIA, ABIA, HBIA and CBIA the colours of the surface films were pink, blackish, steel-grey and coppery, respectively. The films were very stable and so strongly adhered onto the surface of brass that they could not be removed even by rubbing under running water. It may be noted that a pink coloured film composed of Cu^{II} -BIA complex on the surface of brass in ammonia was also reported by Gupta *et al.*⁶. It has been shown⁸ that with copper, BIA forms complexes of the type $Cu^{II}(BIA)_4 \cdot X_2$, where X is a monovalent anion like Cl^- , OH^- etc. BIA has been shown to form complexes with both Cu^I and Cu^{II} and that the complexes are sufficiently stable can be seen from a consideration of the respective formation constants⁹, e.g. the values for Cu^I -BIA complex in 0.15 M Na_2SO_4 solution were found to be $\log K_1=4.47$ and $\log \beta_2=9.73$ and the formation constants for Cu^{II} -BIA complex in 0.15 M $NaClO_4$ solution were shown to be $\log K_1=3.56$, $\log \beta_2=6.34$, $\log \beta_3=9.00$ and $\log \beta_4=10.97$ at 25° Complexes of BIA with zinc¹⁰, $Zn(BIA)_2Cl_2$ and that of ABIA with copper¹¹, $Cu(ABIA)_2Cl_2 \cdot HCl$, have also been reported. In analogy with the Cu -BIA complexes, the remaining inhibitors are also expected to act as ligands in forming stable complexes and thereby inhibit corrosion of brass, though to varying extents. It may be noted in this connection that soluble $Cu^{II}(NH_3)_4^{2+}$ complex was also formed as was evident from the deep blue colour that developed in the corroding media. But the $Cu^{II}(NH_3)_4^{2+}$ complex must not be regarded as participating in the inhibitive process, because corrosion of brass increases with increasing concentration

of ammonia which also promotes formation of the $Cu^{II}(NH_3)_4^{2+}$ complex. Thus, the corrosion inhibition in the present investigation, may be ascribed to the adsorption of the complexes with the inhibitors acting as ligands. Of the three derivatives, ABIA and HBIA are more effective as inhibitors than the parent compound, i.e. BIA, whereas CBIA is less efficient than BIA. This variation in the inhibitive efficiency may be explained by considering their molecular structures.

(BIA)

(ABIA)

(HBIA)

(CBIA)

According to Hackerman and Hurd¹² there exists a correlation between molecular and inhibitive properties of the organic compounds and inhibitive efficiency increases with increasing electron density on the reaction centre of the inhibitor. In BIA the imino N atom acts as the reaction centre through which it forms complex with metal ions and gets adsorbed on to the metal surface. In ABIA and HBIA, the polar atoms, viz. N and O atoms in the *ortho*-positions of ABIA and HBIA respectively, increase the electron density on the imino N atom and thereby enhance the inhibitive efficiency of these two compounds. On the other hand, in CBIA the COOH group is more electronegative than the NH group and acts as an electron-acceptor releasing electrons from the latter. This will reduce the charge density on the reaction centre leading to decrease in the inhibition efficiency of 5-carboxybenzimidazole as compared to that of the parent compound, viz. benzimidazole.

Experimental

Commercial grade 70/30 brass sample (thickness 0.5 mm) containing Cu 69.68%, Zn 30.32%, Fe trace,

Pb nil and Sn nil, as determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Varian AA 1275/1475) was used for the present study. To investigate the inhibitive effect of benzimidazole (BIA), 2-aminobenzimidazole (ABIA), 2-hydroxybenzimidazole (HBIA), and 5-carboxybenzimidazole (CBIA) on the corrosion and dezincification of brass in NH_4OH solution, weight-loss, solution analysis and galvanostatic polarisation techniques were employed. 1, 5, 9 and 13.36 *N* NH_4OH solutions were used as the corroding media and inhibitors were in the concentration range 10^{-6} – 10^{-2} *M*. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solutions were prepared using double-distilled water.

Immersion tests : Specimens (2 cm × 2 cm) were cut from the brass sheet, polished by linen buffing and cleaned with water followed by acetone. In order that the specimens could be uniformly exposed to the corroding solution, each of the specimen held vertically inside a cylindrical glass tube (3.5 cm × 2.2 cm i.d.) open at both ends and having a few holes on its surface, was placed in a conical flask (250 ml) to which was then added 150 ml of the corrodant containing varying amounts of the inhibitors. The flasks were tightly covered so as to minimise loss of ammonia and kept in an air-thermostat maintained at $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$. After immersion for definite periods, the specimens were taken out, cleaned with water, dried and weighed. The percent inhibitive efficiency (P.I.) was calculated using the relation,

$$\text{P.I.} = \frac{W_0 - W}{W_0} \times 100$$

where *W* and *W*₀ are weight-losses of brass with and without inhibitor respectively.

Solution analysis : Solutions left after weight-loss measurements were analysed for Cu and Zn by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The dezincification factor (*Z*) was calculated using the relation¹³,

$$Z = \frac{(\text{Zn/Cu})_{\text{solution}}}{(\text{Zn/Cu})_{\text{alloy}}}$$

where, the ratio $(\text{Zn/Cu})_{\text{solution}}$ is determined from solution analysis and $(\text{Zn/Cu})_{\text{alloy}}$ is the ratio of weight-percent in the alloy.

Galvanostatic polarisation : Flag-shaped working electrodes (2 cm × 1 cm with a 4 cm tag) prepared by cutting the same 70/30 brass sheet were subjected to the same surface treatment as employed earlier. Both sides of the electrodes were exposed to the test solutions so that effective surface area was 4 cm². A platinised platinum foil was used as the counter electrode together with a saturated calomel electrode as reference. The measurements were carried out in a 250 ml corrosion cell containing 100 ml of the corrodant at $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$. Constant

currents, increasing in steps, were applied at intervals of 1 min through a 12 V D.C. battery and variable resistance and the current potential values were recorded by means of a high impedance multimeter (Philips). After obtaining the open-circuit potential, the specimen was first cathodically polarised and the potentials corresponding to the input currents were recorded. After cathodic polarisation, the working electrode was brought back to the open-circuit potential and then polarised anodically to derive the corresponding polarisation curves. Corrosion currents were evaluated by extrapolating the anodic Tafel lines to open-circuit potential. All measurements were repeated till reproducible data were obtained. The percent inhibition efficiency (P.I.) was calculated from the polarisation studies, using the relation,

$$\text{P.I.} = \frac{i_0 - i}{i_0} \times 100$$

where, *i* and *i*₀ are the corrosion currents with and without inhibitor respectively.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the Special Level Instrumentation Centre, Kalyani University, for ungrudging help and cooperation in getting the spectral data and fabricating small equipments. Thanks are also due to the authorities of Kalyani University, for awarding a fellowship to one of the authors (S.K.B.).

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